

INNOVATION CLUSTER OF PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

ABSTRACT

This article examines the research conducted in the framework of the project "Innovative Cluster of Pedagogical Education" in improving the quality and effectiveness of education in the system of continuing education and their analysis and it's importance to apply new approaches to traditional education.

Keywords: continuous educational process, innovative cluster of pedagogical education, school-laboratory innovative experimental platform, initiative students, innovative pedagogical technology

Today, a number of works are being carried out to improve the educational system and ensure the right of citizens to acquire knowledge. If we look at the history of the developed countries of the world, we can see that the reforms aimed at changing the life of society in them began first of all from the educational system, from the issue of kindergarten, school, upbringing. Because there can be no change in a person, in society, without changing the school. The basis of education and upbringing, the foundation-the school. And the power that makes the school a school is the teachers. It is known that in the difficult transition years the optimal and educational environment in schools, the image of the teaching profession, prestige decreased, the upbringing of teachers of a new period, the development of pedagogical science, the introduction of innovative educational technologies did not pay enough attention to a number of serious problems. area. In the following years, a lot of work is being carried out in our country on the effec-

tion of these problems, radical improvement of the system of Personnel Training. The president of our country adopted 4 decrees and resolutions on the system of public education, 20 resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers and strengthened the legal and normative bases of reforms in this sphere [1].

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In particular, according to the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on the strategy of action for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated February 7, 2017, IV direction on priority directions of development of the social sphere, field of education and science of paragraph 4.4. Further improvement of the system of continuous education in accordance with the modern needs of the labor market is defined in it to continue the policy of training highly qualified personnel [2]. In the field of education and training, such important tasks as the creation of a modern and national system, teaching methods, educational standards, the need to update textbooks and teaching aids, the use of advanced foreign experience in teaching knowledge, the reliance on national traditions and values in education are defined. The above tasks, in turn, bear a great responsibility before the educators who provide education in all educational institutions. In order to ensure the implementation of these tasks, the first steps were taken at the Chirchik State Pedagogical Institute of Tashkent region. On the fulfillment of the

tasks set out in the Joint Order of the rectors of the Institute dated 01-235 of April 1, 2019 and the people's Education Department of Tadjikistan signed April 2, 2019. 2 April 11-innovative cluster of pedagogical education "For the 2019-2020 academic year in the general Secondary School of Chirchik city under the Ministry of internal affairs of the Republic of Azerbaijan for the purpose of Organization of the institute as the main strategic research direction and its introduction into practice" initiative students' project on innovation development " school laboratory "Field of experience and

The purpose of the project "innovative cluster of pedagogical education": assistance in increasing the effectiveness of education and training in secondary schools and preschool institutions by establishing the targeted cooperation of institutions directly and indirectly engaged in pedagogical education; organization of systematic work on qualitative satisfaction of the needs of regional pedagogical personnel; reduction of the professional qualification of young specialists; Organization of scientific research on integration, innovation, cohesion, consistency, creating effective cooperation in the field of pedagogical education; organization of experimental-testing processes of scientific-based innovation projects, creating the opportunity to interact with preschool, secondary education and other applicants in the training of pedagogical personnel; integration of resources around topical issues pick up [3-6].

Discussion

In our experience, first of all, the existing problems in the school were studied on the basis of questionnaires. Based on the results of the survey and feedback from the teachers of the institute, the work carried out within the framework of the innovative cluster of pedagogical education was determined. In the course of the study, experimental and test works based on the study of cognitive quality indicators from Zoology with 7th grades were selected and initially experimental and control classes were selected and Mathematical Computational works were determined using Student criterion of Statistics.

The test questionnaire and written work carried out with them on the study of students' knowledge confirmed the results obtained in the quarter. It became known that the quality indicators of the experimental classes increased by 37% in the second quarter entrance test and 79% in the exit test, that is, the quality indicator increased by 22.

Conclusion

In short, as can be seen from the results achieved, the project "innovative cluster of pedagogical education" in the system of continuous education provides the basis for achieving new prospects and opportunities. This in turn serves to improve the quality of education, to obtain continuous knowledge on the basis of full mastering of Sciences and integration of various organizational forms in education.

USED LITERATURE

1. Speech of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the video-projector meeting on the issues of development of the system of public education, increasing the prestige of educators in the profession and society, raising the spirituality of the younger generation on August 23. Newspaper "Ask the People" August 24, 2019.

2. Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan on measures to ensure more effective organization of the process of acquisition of rights over land parcels and other immovable property as part of the South Caucasus pipeline expansion project near ... - "Collection of legislative acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan", 2017. Article 6, Article 70. 3. It Is He Who/What is it? School laboratory methodical manual. Chirchik. 2019. 90 B. 4. Rakhimov A. K. improvement of the methodology for the development of the natural and scientific worldview of students (on the example of teaching the topic "evolutionary teaching"). International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation, Vol. 24, 02, 2020. ISSN: 1475-7192. P. 1283-1296. 5. Rakhimov A. K. formation and development of a scientific worldview in students on the basis of a harmonious approach. // III International Conference "science and society". - Hamilton, Canada, 2018. - P. 71-74. 6. Rakhimov A. G. Theoretical basis for the formation of the natural-scientific worldview of students. // Eastern European scientific journal. - Düsseldorf-Germany, 2017. - No. - What?/50-54.

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